

Developing Cross-Domain Training Materials: Advantages, Challenges, and Framework Refinement

Introduction:

With the emergence of new technologies and methods, organizations must provide training to their employees as a key aspect of change management. Scientific organizations are no exception. Developing training materials and designing course frameworks can be a complex and demanding process. One effective approach is to identify well-developed, openly licensed (Creative Commons BY) courses from other scientific domains and adapt them to suit the needs of our specific domain. This process is referred to as “Developing Cross-Domain Training Materials.” A framework for cross-domain adaptation was developed, ensuring the training materials maintain their quality and meet specific domain needs effectively.

We explored this concept further during a workshop aimed at defining advantages and disadvantages as well as refining the process. This paper provides an overview of the workshop and its outcomes.

Methods

At the "Talking about Education Across Communities at Helmholtz" (TEACH) conference held on November 21–22, 2024, in Berlin, a one-hour workshop was conducted. The nine attendees included a mix of early-career educators (2–5 years) and experienced professionals (6+ years), comprising four PhD holders and five Master’s degree holders.

Participants were engaged in a structured two-part session:

Part 1: Discussing Adaptation vs. Starting from Scratch

This section explored the benefits and challenges of adapting existing training materials versus developing new ones. Participants were introduced to modular training materials, including instructor guides and templates, designed for flexibility and ease of adaptation. A practical example demonstrated how a general text could be tailored to a domain-specific context by identifying key concepts, analyzing their relevance, and adjusting content to suit the audience's baseline knowledge. A discussion followed, where participants debated whether they would prefer to adapt open and adaptable materials or create new ones, weighing the advantages and disadvantages of each approach.

Highlights of discussion:

- Advantages of Adapting Existing Materials:
 - Provides a structure, saving time.
 - Builds on the experience of others and avoids critical errors.
 - Allows iterative improvements to enhance quality.
- Disadvantages of Adapting:
 - Materials may become outdated.
 - Adaptation can be time-consuming and may limit creativity.
 - Risks redundancy with existing materials.
- Advantages of Starting from Scratch:
 - Encourages creativity and innovation.
 - Easier to align with personal teaching methods and other courses.
 - Enables the introduction of unique perspectives.

Part 2: Framework Evaluation

In the second part, participants were introduced to the proposed framework for adapting training materials (graph 1).

Graph 1: The proposed framework for adapting training materials

The evaluation process involved presenting participants with the framework for adapting training materials across domains, provided as hard copies. Using a color-coded system—green for relevant and clear, yellow for somewhat relevant or clear, and red for not relevant or clear—participants individually assessed each component to minimize peer pressure and bias.

Results:

Tables 1: Relevance

	Components	Relevant (count)	Somewhat Relevant(count)	Overall Relevance Percentage	Not Relevant percentage
1	Initial Content Analysis	8	1	100.0%	0.0%
2	Search on Concepts and Consult Domain Experts or Stakeholders	8	1	100.0%	0.0%
3	Assess Audience Knowledge and Needs	7	2	100.0%	0.0%
4	Simplify Language and Focus on Core Points	5	4	100.0%	0.0%
5	Replace General Examples with Domain-Specific Ones	6	3	100.0%	0.0%
6	Pilot and Gather Feedback	7	1	100.0%	0.0%
7	Review for Clarity and Relevance	8	0	88.9%	11.1%
8	Document Adaptation Process	5	4	100.0%	0.0%

Relevance: Most participants agreeing that the components were either relevant or somewhat relevant.

Table 2: Clarity

	Component	Clear (count)	Somewhat clear (count)	Overall clarity percentage	Not clear
1	Initial Content Analysis	6	2	88.9%	11.1%
2	Search on Concepts and Consult Domain Experts or Stakeholders	4	4	88.9%	11.1%
3	Assess Audience Knowledge and Needs	5	3	88.9%	11.1%
4	Simplify Language and Focus on Core Points	4	4	88.9%	11.1%
5	Replace General Examples with Domain-Specific Ones	7	1	88.9%	11.1%
6	Pilot and Gather Feedback	7	1	88.9%	11.1%
7	Review for Clarity and Relevance	8	1	100.0%	0.0%
8	Document Adaptation Process	7	1	88.9%	11.1%

Clarity: 88% of participants found the components clear, with 11% identifying areas requiring clarification.

Key discussion points of Focus Group Discussion:

- Suggestions to improve the clarity of specific components.
- Agreement that the framework is comprehensive, with no additional steps required.
- Emphasis on the importance of iterative cycles to refine the process further.

Framework Refinement:

Based on feedback, the framework was modified to incorporate clearer definitions and an iterative cycle approach. The updated framework is presented in Graph 2.

Graph 2- Refined framework for adapting training material

Conclusion

This two-part workshop successfully gathered insights into the trade-offs between adaptation and starting from scratch, while also evaluating and refining the proposed framework. The process not only validated the framework's relevance but also highlighted the importance of clarity and iterative refinement in adapting training materials for diverse domains.